

REPORT

A.2.2.5: Validation of the fitness of purpose of the performance assessment protocol developed in A2.1.4 by demonstrating its applicability for sulphur compounds

REPORT

A.2.2.5: Validation of SI-traceable performance evaluation of the GC-FID-SCD measurement system that is used for biomethane conformity assessment by demonstrating its applicability for sulphur compounds.

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1. Introduction

In order to meet the requirements of biomethane gas quality standards EN 16723-1 and EN 16723-2, reliable and traceable purity analysis of biomethane is required.

This document describes methods for evaluating instrument performance, specific to biomethane applications in case of sulphur compounds.

Here, this performance assessment protocol was validated using the method ISO 19739:2019 Natural gas — Determination of sulfur compounds using gas chromatography. Specially using capillary column with Sulfur Chemiluminescence Detector, SCD (B.11) and Flame Ionisation Detector, FID.

The validation parameters evaluated here were selectivity, limit of detection and quantification, working range and linearity, trueness/bias, and precision. Using these results, the measurement uncertainty was calculated for each component.

2. Materials and methods

An 7890 Agilent GC FID detects most organic compounds, while combusts samples at a continuous flame as they exit the GC column. One of the combustion products under these flame conditions is a hydronium ion (CHO^+), which is attracted to a polarized collector, creating an ion current that is measured by an electrometer.

The Agilent 8355 SCD, Sulfur Chemiluminescence detection is a dual-plasma burner achieves high temperature combustion of sulfur-containing compounds to form sulfur monoxide (SO). A photomultiplier tube detects the light produced by the chemiluminescent reaction of SO with ozone.

J&W DB-1 is nonpolar and low-bleed GC column that operates at 23 C temperature; 30 m x 0.320 ID x 1 μm film.

Sampling: every 5 minutes

The reference mixture produced by BFKH as pre-dilution gas mixture for gas prepared in WP1 diluted with methane using a CMK calibrator.

Compounds and the range of concentration after the dilution:

S1: hydrogen sulphide (0.5 -3.5 ppm),

S2: methyl mercaptan, S3: dimethyl sulphide, S4: ethyl mercaptan, S5: ethyl methyl sulphide, S6: diethyl sulphide (0.1-0.7 ppm).

3. Validation

General overview

The general procedure for determining the performance characteristics of the instrument is summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. Four steps with general procedure for determination of the performance characteristics.

Step	Phase	Description	Results
1	Planning	Specify the components required to be measured by the instrument and the measurement range for each over which the instrument shall be evaluated.	All sulphur compounds, but the validation will be done for hydrogen sulphide, methyl mercaptan, ethyl methyl sulphide, ethyl mercaptan, dimethyl sulphide, diethyl sulphide.
2	Planning	Establish the functional descriptions of the response functions assumed by the instrument for each specified component.	The response should be linear.
3	Planning	Specify a set of reference gas mixtures (calibration gases) with compositions covering all ranges for all components specified in step 1.	Only one gas mixture will be used: BFKH mixture prepared at WP1 as pre-diluted mixture
4	Planning	Establish the composition and uncertainty of the calibration gas mixture(s) to be used for routine calibration of the instrument.	$x_{ref} = 0.1 - 0.7 \text{ ppm} \pm 5-10 \% \text{ rel}$ uncertainty per compound

The extent of the performance characteristic validation is summarised in Table 2.

Table 2. Extent of validation.

Performance characteristic	Analytical application		
	Component identification	Component detection	Component quantification
Selectivity	x	x	x
Limit of detection		x	
Limit of quantification			x
Working range			x
Trueness			x
Precision			x
Rise time			Not applicable
Memory effect and fall time			Not applicable

Selectivity

The selectivity of the method was investigated by studying its ability how to measure the interest analyte in the sample wick contains 6 closely similar compounds. The method should be optimized to avoid co-elution of the analyte of interest between eachother in the sample. Using GC parameters in this method, the following chromatogram was obtained.

Figure 1. Gas chromatogram of a sulphur compounds at SCD

Figure 2. Gas chromatogram of a sulphur compounds at FID

Resolution was calculated according to this equation [1]:

$$\frac{t_{R2} - t_{R1}}{\frac{1}{2}(W_1 + W_2)}$$

Where t_{R2} , t_{R1} are retention time for each peak and W_1 , W_2 are width of each peak. A resolution of 1.5 or more occurs when the signal returns to its baseline between two peaks, indicating good separation.

Table 3. Resolution SCD

Detector	Compound	t_{Ri}	W_i	Resolution	R
SCD	S1 hydrogen sulphide	110.581	0.0386	S1-S2	4.8
	S2 methyl mercaptan	110.741	0.0284	S2-S3	9.5
	S3 dimethyl sulphide	111.017	0.03	S3-S4	2.8
	S4 ethyl mercaptan	111.095	0.0259	S4-S5	28.5
	S5 ethyl methyl sulphide	111.969	0.0354	S5-S6	39.9
	S6 diethyl sulphide	113.934	0.063		

All peaks are well separated with a resolution greater than 1.5.

Table 4. Resolution FID

Detector	Compound	t_{Ri}	W_i	Resolution	R
FID	S3 dimethyl sulphide	111.009	0.0277	S3-S4	3.2
	S4 ethyl mercaptan	111.092	0.0248	S4-S5	29.2
	S5 ethyl methyl sulphide	111.966	0.0351	S5-S6	38.9
	S6 diethyl sulphide	113.931	0.0658		

All peaks are well separated with a resolution greater than 1.5.

Limit of detection and quantification

For the LOD and LOQ are calculated via replicate measurements of test samples with a suitably low amount fraction of the analyte.

The limit of detection and quantification (LOD and LOQ) for the sulphur compounds was calculated with a Signal-to-Noise (S/N) approach. The S/N ratio is determined by comparing signals from samples with known low amount of analyte with those of blank samples. LOD and LOQ is the determination of the minimum amount at which the analyte can be confidently detected and quantified. The LOD is determined for $S/N = 3$ and the LOQ for $S/N = 10$. The results are presented in Table 5. The results show that the method is sensitive and can be used to analyze samples with low amount fractions of sulphur compounds.

Table 5. Calculated limits of detection and quantification for sulphur compounds SCD

Compounds SCD	Target amount ppm	Noise pA	Signal pA	S/N at target amount	LOD ppm (S/N = 3)	LOQ ppm (S/N = 10)
hydrogen sulphide	0.50	1.3	299	230	0.005	0.017
methyl mercaptan	0.10	1.3	58.6	45	0.005	0.018
dimethyl sulphide	0.10	1.3	13.4	10	0.025	0.083
ethyl mercaptan	0.10	1.3	1056	812	0.000	0.001
ethyl methyl sulphide	0.10	1.3	707	544	0.000	0.001
diethyl sulphide	0.10	1.3	330	254	0.001	0.003

Table 6. Calculated limits of detection and quantification for sulphur compounds FID

Compounds FID	Target amount ppm	Noise pA	Signal pA	S/N at target amount	LOD ppm (S/N = 3)	LOQ ppm (S/N = 10)
dimethyl sulphide	0.10	0.02	1	50	0.306	1.020
ethyl mercaptan	0.10	0.02	3	150	0.101	0.336
ethyl methyl sulphide	0.10	0.02	3.3	165	0.081	0.305
diethyl sulphide	0.10	0.02	2.4	120	0.126	0.420

Working range and linearity

S1 Hydrogen sulphide

The linearity was analyzed originally 7 different amounts in ppm hydrogen sulphide from 0.5-3.5. Samples from 0.5 to 1.5 ppm didn't given good results. Results for hydrogen sulphide measured in the range 2 to 3.7 ppm are shown in Figure 3.

This sort range the correlation coefficient of the linear line for hydrogen sulphide measured with GC-SCD is close to a value of 1.00, suggesting that the equation for the linear regression fits the data. This observation implies that the method encompasses a linear working range within 2 to 3.7 ppm.

Figure 3. Correlation between the area measured with SCD detector and the known amount of sample in ppm.

Figure 4. The residual of the difference between calculated area and measured area in GC-SCD plotted against known amount of sample in ppm.

The distribution of residuals is random, confirming the linearity and working range (figure 4).

S2 Methyl mercaptan

The linearity was analyzed originally 7 different amounts in ppm methyl mercaptan from 0.102-0.718. Samples from 0.102-0.205 ppm didn't given good results. Results for methyl mercaptan measured in the range 0.308 to 0.718 ppm are shown in Figure 5.

This sort range the correlation coefficient of the linear line for methyl mercaptan measured with GC-SCD is close to a value of 1.00, suggesting that the equation for the linear regression fits the data. This observation implies that the method encompasses a linear working range within 0.308 to 0.718 ppm.

Figure 5. Correlation between the area measured with SCD detector and the known amount of sample in ppm.

Figure 6. The residual of the difference between calculated area and measured area in GC-SCD plotted against known amount of sample in ppm.

The distribution of residuals is random, confirming the linearity and working range (figure 6).

S3 Dimethyl sulphide

The linearity was analyzed 7 different amounts in ppm dimethyl sulphide from 0.105- 0.732. Results for dimethyl sulphide measured in the range 0.105- 0.732 ppm with FID and SCD are shown in Figure 7.

This range the correlation coefficients of the linear lines for dimethyl sulphide measured with GC-SCD and GC-FID are close to a value of 1.00, suggesting that the equation for the linear regression fits the data. This observation implies that the method encompasses a linear working range within 0.105- 0.732 ppm.

Figure 7. Correlation between the area measured with FID and SCD detector and the known amount of sample in ppm.

Figure 8. The residual of the difference between calculated area and measured area in GC-SCD plotted against known amount of sample in ppm.

The distribution of residuals is random, confirming the linearity and working range (figure 8).

S4 Ethyl mercaptan

The linearity was analyzed 7 different amounts in ppm ethyl mercaptan from 0.102- 0.711.

Results for ethyl mercaptan measured in the range 0.102- 0.711 ppm are shown in Figure 9.

This range the correlation coefficients of the linear lines for ethyl mercaptan measured with GC-SCD and GC-FID are close to a value of 1.00, suggesting that the equation for the linear regression fits the data. This observation implies that the method encompasses a linear working range within 0.102- 0.711 ppm.

Figure 9. Correlation between the area measured with FID and SCD detector and the known amount of sample in ppm.

Figure 10. The residual of the difference between calculated area and measured area in GC-SCD plotted against known amount of sample in ppm.

The distribution of residuals is random, confirming the linearity and working range (figure 10).

S5 Ethyl methyl sulphide

The linearity was analyzed 7 different amounts in ppm ethyl methyl sulphide from 0.105- 0.735.

Results for ethyl methyl sulphide measured in the range 0.105- 0.735 ppm are shown in Figure 11.

This range the correlation coefficients of the linear lines for ethyl methyl sulphide measured with GC-SCD and GC-FID are close to a value of 1.00, suggesting that the equation for the linear regression fits the data. This observation implies that the method encompasses a linear working range within 0.105- 0.735 ppm.

Figure 11. Correlation between the area measured with FID and SCD detector and the known amount of sample in ppm.

Figure 12. The residual of the difference between calculated area and measured area in GC-SCD plotted against known amount of sample in ppm.

The distribution of residuals is random, confirming the linearity and working range (figure 12).

S6 Diethyl sulphide

The linearity was analyzed 7 different amounts in ppm diethyl sulphide from 0.108- 0.753.

Results for diethyl sulphide measured in the range 0.108- 0.753 ppm are shown in Figure 13.

This range the correlation coefficients of the linear lines for diethyl sulphide measured with GC-SCD and GC-FID are close to a value of 1.00, suggesting that the equation for the linear regression fits the data. This observation implies that the method encompasses a linear working range within 0.108- 0.753 ppm.

Figure 13. Correlation between the area measured with FID and SCD detector and the known amount of sample in ppm.

Figure 14. The residual of the difference between calculated area and measured area in GC-SCD plotted against known amount of sample in ppm.

The distribution of residuals is random, confirming the linearity and working range (figure 14).

Trueness, Bias

Evaluation against a reference material: compare mean measured value, with the reference value for the reference material. Calculate bias, relative bias, or the relative recovery (apparent recovery)

The differences between the calculated concentrations and the expected concentrations are minimal. Thus, the biases are negligible, as shown in Tables 7-12.

Table 7. Bias calculated for hydrogen sulphide SCD

Results ppm	Expected results ppm	Bias ppm	Relative Bias
2.0	1.955	-0.045	-0.02
2.0	1.978	-0.022	-0.01
2.0	2.064	0.064	0.03
2.0	1.953	-0.047	-0.02
2.0	1.929	-0.071	-0.04
	Mean	-0.024	-0.012

Table 8. Bias calculated for methyl mercaptan SCD

Results ppm	Expected results ppm	Bias ppm	Relative Bias
0.387	0.372	-0.015	-0.039
0.387	0.400	0.013	0.033
0.387	0.368	-0.019	-0.048
0.387	0.372	-0.015	-0.038
0.387	0.379	-0.008	-0.019
	Mean	-0.009	-0.022

Table 9. Bias calculated for dimethyl sulphide FID and SCD

Expected results ppm	Results FID ppm	Bias FID ppm	Relative Bias FID	Results SCD ppm	Bias SCD ppm	Relative Bias SCD
0.383	0.376	-0.007	-0.017	0.377	-0.006	-0.016
0.383	0.385	0.002	0.006	0.374	-0.009	-0.023
0.383	0.383	0.000	0.001	0.373	-0.010	-0.026
0.383	0.389	0.006	0.016	0.372	-0.011	-0.029
0.383	0.378	-0.005	-0.013	0.379	-0.004	-0.010
	Mean	0	0	Mean	-0.008	-0.021

Table 10. Bias calculated for ethyl mercaptan FID and SCD

Expected results ppm	Results FID ppm	Bias FID ppm	Relative Bias FID	Results SCD ppm	Bias SCD ppm	Relative Bias SCD
0.396	0.393	-0.003	-0.008	0.398	0.002	0.005
0.396	0.400	0.004	0.010	0.393	-0.003	-0.007
0.396	0.394	-0.002	-0.005	0.387	-0.009	-0.022
0.396	0.399	0.003	0.007	0.396	0.000	0.000
0.396	0.394	-0.002	-0.006	0.394	-0.002	-0.006
	Mean	0	0	Mean	-0.002	-0.006

Table 11. Bias calculated for ethyl methyl sulphide FID and SCD

Expected results ppm	Results FID ppm	Bias FID ppm	Relative Bias FID	Results SCD ppm	Bias SCD ppm	Relative Bias SCD
0.394	0.393	-0.001	-0.002	0.393	-0.001	-0.003
0.394	0.391	-0.003	-0.007	0.394	0.000	-0.001
0.394	0.397	0.003	0.008	0.394	0.000	0.001
0.394	0.399	0.005	0.013	0.391	-0.003	-0.007
0.394	0.391	-0.003	-0.007	0.393	-0.001	-0.003
	Mean	0	0	Mean	-0.001	-0.002

Table 12. Bias calculated for diethyl sulphide FID and SCD

Expected results ppm	Results FID ppm	Bias FID ppm	Relative Bias FID	Results SCD ppm	Bias SCD ppm	Relative Bias SCD
0.406	0.403	-0.003	-0.008	0.401	-0.005	-0.012
0.406	0.407	0.001	0.004	0.405	-0.001	-0.003
0.406	0.408	0.002	0.004	0.405	-0.001	-0.002
0.406	0.411	0.005	0.012	0.404	-0.002	-0.004
0.406	0.410	0.004	0.011	0.404	-0.002	-0.005
	Mean	0	0	Mean	-0.002	-0.005

Precision

Precision was assessed by measuring 10 duplicates of sulphur compounds's mixture at varying quantities using GC-FID/SCD on several days. Standard deviation, as well as relative standard deviation, were determined and the pooled standard deviation was calculated. The results can be found in Table 13-19.

Table 13. Estimation of the intermediate precision for hydrogen sulphide using GC-SCD

Replicates	Meas. 1 ppm	Meas. 2 ppm	S ppm	CV
1 (241206)	1.955	1.978	0.016	0.83
2 (241206)	2.428	2.462	0.024	0.98
3 (241206)	3.052	3.089	0.026	0.85
4 (241209)	2.220	2.195	0.018	0.80
5 (241209)	3.098	3.056	0.030	0.97
6 (241210)	2.003	1.973	0.021	1.07
7 (241210)	3.471	3.499	0.020	0.57
8 (241216)	2.012	2.058	0.033	1.60
9 (241216)	2.499	2.446	0.037	1.52
10(241216)	3.536	3.548	0.008	0.24
			sr%	0.94

Table 14. Estimation of the intermediate precision for methyl mercaptan using GC-SCD

Replicates	Meas. 1 ppm	Meas. 2 ppm	S ppm	CV
1 (241206)	0.387	0.399	0.008	2.16
2 (241206)	0.478	0.462	0.011	2.41
3 (241209)	0.565	0.581	0.011	1.97
4 (241209)	0.672	0.660	0.008	1.27
5 (241210)	0.298	0.291	0.005	1.68
6 (241210)	0.482	0.489	0.005	1.02
7 (241210)	0.675	0.686	0.008	1.14
8 (241216)	0.301	0.309	0.006	1.85

9 (241216)	0.586	0.574	0.008	1.46
10(241216)	0.668	0.679	0.008	1.15
			sr%	1.7

Table 15. Estimation of the intermediate precision for ethyl-mercaptan using GC-SCD

Replicates	Meas. 1 ppm	Meas. 2 ppm	S ppm	CV
1 (241206)	0.691	0.678	0.009	1.34
2 (241206)	0.487	0.498	0.008	1.58
3 (241209)	0.579	0.594	0.011	1.81
4 (241209)	0.681	0.699	0.013	1.84
5 (241210)	0.198	0.204	0.004	2.11
6 (241210)	0.297	0.303	0.004	1.41
7 (241210)	0.396	0.410	0.010	2.46
8 (241216)	0.195	0.200	0.004	1.79
9 (241216)	0.291	0.300	0.006	2.15
10(241216)	0.596	0.606	0.007	1.18
			sr%	1.77

Table 16. Estimation of the intermediate precision for dimethyl sulphide using GC-SCD

Replicates	Meas. 1 ppm	Meas. 2 ppm	S ppm	CV
1 (241206)	0.292	0.279	0.009	3.22
2 (241206)	0.478	0.490	0.008	1.75
3 (241206)	0.593	0.602	0.006	1.07
4 (241209)	0.388	0.398	0.007	1.80
5 (241209)	0.58	0.589	0.006	1.09
6 (241209)	0.687	0.699	0.008	1.22
7 (241210)	0.289	0.283	0.004	1.48
8 (241210)	0.385	0.38	0.004	0.92

9 (241216)	0.292	0.299	0.005	1.68
10(241216)	0.394	0.405	0.008	1.95
			sr%	1.62

Table 17. Estimation of the intermediate precision for ethyl-methyl sulphide using GC-SCD

Replicates	Meas. 1 ppm	Meas. 2 ppm	S ppm	CV
1 (241206)	0.570	0.561	0.006	1.13
2 (241206)	0.686	0.697	0.008	1.12
3 (241209)	0.489	0.475	0.010	2.05
4 (241209)	0.557	0.571	0.010	1.76
5 (241210)	0.275	0.284	0.006	2.28
6 (241210)	0.377	0.371	0.004	1.13
7 (241210)	0.463	0.473	0.007	1.51
8 (241216)	0.301	0.291	0.007	2.39
9 (241216)	0.394	0.401	0.005	1.25
10(241216)	0.482	0.492	0.007	1.45
			sr%	1.61

Table 18. Estimation of the intermediate precision for diethyl sulphide using GC-SCD

Replicates	Meas. 1 ppm	Meas. 2 ppm	S ppm	CV
1 (241206)	0.718	0.732	0.010	1.37
2 (241209)	0.389	0.400	0.008	1.97
3 (241209)	0.621	0.602	0.013	2.20
4 (241209)	0.717	0.732	0.011	1.46
5 (241210)	0.103	0.100	0.002	2.09
6 (241210)	0.310	0.321	0.008	2.47
7 (241210)	0.300	0.308	0.006	1.86

8 (241210)	0.603	0.621	0.013	2.08
9 (241216)	0.113	0.109	0.003	2.55
10(241216)	0.200	0.205	0.004	1.75
			sr%	1.98

Measurement uncertainties

The expanded uncertainties ($k=2$) were calculated. In general, measurement uncertainty of 10% or less are considered reliable at this ranges. The calculations show that measurement uncertainties are lower than 10 % and the method can therefore be considered reliable (Table 19).

- $u(R_w)$ uncertainty from within-lab reproducibility
- $u(b)$ uncertainty from bias components
- $k=2$ assigned coverage factor for degree of equivalence
- $U_{i,x}$ stated uncertainty at 95 % level of confidence

Table 19. Within-laboratory reproducibility, method biases and expanded uncertainties from the GC-SCD/FID system for sulphur compounds.

Compounds	$u(R_w)$ rel %	$u(\text{bias})$ rel %	$U = 2u_c$ rel%
hydrogen sulphide	0.94	2.63	5.59
methyl mercaptan	1.7	3.68	8.11
dimethyl sulphide	1.77	2.18	5.62
ethyl mercaptan	1.62	1.11	3.93
ethyl methyl sulphide	1.61	0.36	3.30
diethyl sulphide	1.98	0.61	4.14

4. Conclusions

This report describes methods for evaluating instrument performance, specific to biomethane applications in case of sulphur compounds as, hydrogen sulphide (0.5 -3.7 ppm), methyl mercaptan, dimethyl sulphide, ethyl mercaptan, ethyl methyl sulphide, diethyl sulphide (0.1-0.8 ppm).

In order to meet the requirements of biomethane gas quality standards EN 16723-1 and EN 16723-2, reliable and traceable purity analysis of biomethane is required.

Here, this performance assessment protocol was validated using the method ISO 19739:2019 Natural gas — Determination of sulfur compounds using gas chromatography. Specially using capillary column with Sulfur Chemiluminescence Detector, SCD (B.11) and Flame Ionisation Detector, FID.

The validation parameters evaluated here were selectivity, limit of detection and quantification, working range and linearity, trueness/bias, and precision. Using these results, the measurement uncertainty was calculated for each component.

The method is therefore found to be fit-for-purpose, reliable and highly sensitive. As the working range is at least 0.1 to 3.7 ppm, it can be used to analyze samples with amount fractions of sulphur compounds from 0.1 to 3.7 ppm.

5. References

ISO 19739:2019 Natural gas — Determination of sulphur compounds using gas chromatography.

REPORT

A.2.2.1: Validation of the fitness of purpose of the performance assessment protocol developed in A2.1.4 by demonstrating its applicability for sulphur components in methane with GC-SCD using the own static standards produced

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1. Introduction

The BiometCAP project is developing a performance assessment protocol (A2.1.4) for evaluating instruments and methods used for biomethane conformity assessment. Here, this performance assessment protocol was tested and validated using the method based on ISO 19739 for the determination of sulphur components in biomethane matrices.

The method is based on gas chromatography with a sulphur chemiluminescence detector.

The validation parameters evaluated here were selectivity, limit of detection and quantification, working range and linearity, trueness/bias, and precision. Using these results, the measurement uncertainty was calculated for each component.

2. Materials and methods

For analysis the gas chromatograph with sulphur chemiluminescence detector was used (plumbing diagram in annex 1).

The analysis utilized column from Agilent - Agilent 19091Z-613, length 30 m, diameter 0.32 mm.

Reference mixture produced by CMI in methane matrix.

Analysed sulphur components:

- hydrogen sulphide
- COS - Carbonyl sulphide
- methanethiol
- ethanethiol
- DMS - Dimethyl sulphide
- TBM - tert-butyl mercaptan
- THT – tetrahydrothiophene

3. Validation

General overview

The general procedure for determining the performance characteristics of the instrument is summarised in table 1. Detailed process descriptions are provided in the following sections.

table 1 Overview of performance evaluation process

Step	Phase	Description	Document section reference	
1	Planning	Specify the components required to be measured by the instrument and the measurement range for each over which the instrument shall be evaluated.	Sulphur components	
2	Planning	Establish the functional descriptions of the response functions assumed by the instrument for each specified component.	The response should be linear.	
3	Planning	Specify a set of reference gas mixtures (calibration gases) with compositions covering all ranges for all components specified in step 1.	Own reference materials	
4	Planning	Establish the composition and uncertainty of the calibration gas mixture(s) to be used for routine calibration of the instrument.	Sulphur content	0,5 - 6
			(Only sulphur content in mg/m ³)	

The extent of the performance characteristic validation is summarised in table 2.

table 2 extent of validation

Performance characteristic	Analytical application		
	Component identification	Component detection	Component quantification
Selectivity	x	x	x
Limit of detection		x	
Limit of quantification			x
Working range			x
Trueness			x
Precision			x
Rise time			Not applicable
Memory effect and fall time			Not applicable

Based on previous experiences, for this method, the targeted relative within-laboratory reproducibility, $u(R_w)$, is set at 5 % and the targeted relative bias, $u(\text{bias})$, is set at 10 %.

Selectivity

Here we used a reference mixture sample containing the interest components.

The selectivity of the method was investigated by studying its ability to measure the analyte of interest in the sample.

The method should be optimized to avoid co-elution of the analyte of interest and the other components present in the sample.

With the selected GC parameters for this method with SCD detector, the following chromatogram was obtained for a mixture sample (Figure 1).

Figure 1 chromatogram shows that sulphur components eluates good separated

Limit of detection and quantification

In this case, the method “replicate measurements of test samples with a suitably low amount fraction of the analyte” was chosen.

The limit of detection and quantification (LOD and LOQ) for sulphur components was calculated with a Signal-to-Noise (S/N) approach. The S/N ratio is determined by comparing the signals from samples with known low amount of analyte with those of blank samples. LOD and LOQ is the determination of the minimum amount at which the analyte can be confidently detected and quantified. Here, the LOD is determined for $S/N = 3$ and the LOQ for $S/N = 10$. The results are presented in table 3.

The results show that the method is sensitive and can be used to analyse samples with low amount interest components.

table 3 Calculated limits of detection and quantification.

Compounds	Target amount	Noise	Signal	S/N at target amount	LOD	LOQ
	(mg/m ³)	(-)	(-)		(mg/m ³)	(mg/m ³)
					(S/N = 3)	(S/N = 10)
hydrogen sulphide	3,42	30	17289,6	576,32	0,018	0,059
COS	4,78	20	13946,2	697,31	0,021	0,068
methanthiol	4,13	20	17825,1	891,26	0,014	0,046
ethanethiol	4,07	25	16216,0	648,64	0,019	0,063
DMS	2,52	25	10200,9	408,04	0,019	0,062
TBM	3,43	22	8862,1	402,82	0,026	0,085
THT	4,28	30	12541,9	418,06	0,031	0,102

Working range and linearity

The linearity was assessed by analysing different amounts interested compounds (mg/m^3) for all components.

The results for sulphur components measured in the range 0,5 -6 mg/m^3 (only sulphur) are shown in Figure 2.

As can be seen in Figure 1, the correlation coefficient for sulphur components measured with GC-SCD is close to a value of 1.00, suggesting that the equation for the linear regression fits the data. This observation implies that the method encompasses a linear working range within 0,5 to 6 mg/m^3 .

The distribution of residuals is random, confirming the linearity and working range (Figure 3).

Figure 2 Correlation between the area measured with SCD detector and the known amount of sample in mg/m^3

Figure 3 The residual of the difference between calculated area and measured area in GC-SCD plotted against known amount of sample in mg/m^3

Trueness, Bias

Since it is not possible to take an infinite number of measurements, trueness cannot be measured. A practical assessment of the trueness can however be made. This assessment is normally expressed evaluation against a reference material.

Compare mean measured value, \bar{x} with the reference value x_{ref} or the reference material. Calculate bias, b , per cent relative bias, $b(\%)$ or the relative per cent recovery (apparent recovery) $R(\%)$.

$$b = \bar{x} - x_{ref}$$

$$b(\%) = \frac{\bar{x} - x_{ref}}{x_{ref}} \times 100$$

$$R(\%) = \frac{\bar{x}}{x_{ref}} \times 100$$

The differences between the calculated concentrations and the expected concentrations are presented in table 4 - table 8.

table 4 Bias calculated for hydrogen sulphide

Results	Reference value	Bias	relative BIAS
5,91	5,99	-0,086	-1,43
5,86	5,99	-0,138	-2,30
5,90	5,99	-0,092	-1,53
5,91	5,99	-0,084	-1,41
5,94	5,99	-0,057	-0,95
	mean	-0,091	-1,53

table 5 Bias calculated for COS

Results	Reference value	Bias	relative BIAS
1,43	1,48	-0,053	-3,57
1,37	1,48	-0,106	-7,20
1,44	1,48	-0,039	-2,66
1,45	1,48	-0,029	-1,99
1,44	1,48	-0,041	-2,78
	mean	-0,054	-3,64

table 6 Bias calculated for methanethiol

Results	Reference value	Bias	relative BIAS
3,97	4,13	-0,156	-3,78
4,02	4,13	-0,108	-2,61
4,06	4,13	-0,065	-1,57
4,01	4,13	-0,115	-2,79
4,01	4,13	-0,115	-2,79
	mean	-0,112	-2,71

table 7 Bias calculated for ethanethiol

Results	Reference value	Bias	relative BIAS
4,10	3,99	0,107	2,69
4,09	3,99	0,100	2,51
4,17	3,99	0,181	4,55
4,19	3,99	0,200	5,00
4,07	3,99	0,082	2,05
	mean	0,134	3,36

table 8 Bias calculated for tetrahydrothiophene

Results	Reference value	Bias	relative BIAS
12,78	12,34	0,439	3,56
12,69	12,34	0,346	2,80
12,88	12,34	0,544	4,41
12,77	12,34	0,427	3,46
12,85	12,34	0,515	4,17
	mean	0,454	3,68

Precision

Protocol: To evaluate repeatability, measure the analyte(s) of interest within a reference material at various concentrations spread across the working range using the same method. Obtain at least 10 replicate measurements and calculate the standard deviation and relative standard deviation.

Precision was assessed by measuring 10 duplicates of hydrogen, oxygen, carbon monoxide, nitrogen and methane on several days. Standard deviation, as well as relative standard deviation were calculated. The results are presented in table 9 - table 13.

table 9 Estimation of the intermediate precision for hydrogen sulphide

Replicates	Meas. 1	Meas. 2	S	CV
1	3,41	3,71	0,217	4,316
2	3,54	3,29	0,180	3,728
3	3,01	3,21	0,143	3,265
4	4,43	4,79	0,254	3,898
5	4,42	4,78	0,252	3,869
6	5,61	5,95	0,240	2,937
7	5,45	5,59	0,101	1,288
8	5,38	5,48	0,072	0,938
9	5,26	5,66	0,288	3,725
10	5,38	5,86	0,340	4,278
			mean	3,224

table 10 Estimation of the intermediate precision for COS

Replicates	Meas. 1	Meas. 2	S	CV
1	4,96	4,81	0,102	1,478
2	4,96	4,74	0,160	2,337
3	4,57	4,69	0,086	1,311
4	2,76	2,87	0,075	1,895
5	2,82	2,75	0,052	1,308
6	1,37	1,49	0,085	4,214
7	1,45	1,42	0,024	1,161
8	1,45	1,45	0,003	0,126
9	1,41	1,47	0,046	2,246
10	1,61	1,42	0,133	6,192
			mean	2,227

table 11 Estimation of the intermediate precision for methanethiol

Replicates	Meas. 1	Meas. 2	S	CV
1	4,02	4,07	0,039	0,683
2	4,01	4,07	0,045	0,791
3	4,05	3,81	0,169	3,040
4	4,07	3,71	0,257	4,675
5	3,71	3,90	0,134	2,494
6	3,70	3,90	0,148	2,754
7	3,64	3,75	0,082	1,562
8	4,05	4,33	0,196	3,302
9	4,09	4,11	0,010	0,176
10	4,05	4,03	0,014	0,248
			mean	1,972

table 12 Estimation of the intermediate precision for ethanethiol

Replicates	Meas. 1	Meas. 2	S	CV
1	3,89	4,03	0,101	1,805
2	4,06	3,86	0,140	2,502
3	3,57	3,79	0,152	2,910
4	3,64	3,86	0,161	3,036
5	3,64	3,75	0,080	1,539
6	3,57	3,65	0,058	1,131
7	3,94	4,22	0,198	3,422
8	3,99	3,99	0,000	0,001
9	4,06	4,04	0,014	0,237
10	3,84	4,11	0,195	3,463
			mean	2,005

table 13 Estimation of the intermediate precision for tetrahydrothiophene

Replicates	Meas. 1	Meas. 2	S	CV
1	5,03	4,69	0,238	3,458
2	5,06	4,94	0,088	1,250
3	4,89	4,96	0,054	0,775
4	4,80	4,93	0,096	1,397
5	4,86	4,81	0,036	0,524
6	4,93	4,80	0,092	1,333
7	4,26	4,28	0,015	0,241
8	4,25	4,19	0,039	0,651
9	12,79	12,84	0,033	0,180
10	12,90	12,89	0,010	0,056
			mean	0,986

Measurement uncertainties

The expanded uncertainty (k=2) for compounds was calculated using the following formula:

$$u_a(x_i) = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{j=1}^n (x_j - x_i)^2}{N \cdot (N-1)}}$$

$$u_b(x_i) = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^m u_{RMj}^2}$$

$$u_c(x_i) = \sqrt{u_a(x_i)^2 + u_b(x_i)^2}$$

$$U_{(xi)} = k \cdot u_{c(xi)}$$

Where:

- u_a – uncertainty from measurement
- u_b – uncertainties from reference materials
- u_c - combined standard uncertainty
- U_{xi} - expanded standard uncertainty
- k - expansion coefficient
- u_{RMj} - uncertainty of reference material
- x_i - mole fraction of component i
- N - number of measurements

In general for a GC method for this compounds the measurement uncertainty of 10% or less is considered as acceptable and the method is reliable.

The reference and measured value was compared using the parameter E_n

$$E_n = \frac{y_{lab} - y_{ref}}{\sqrt{U_{lab}^2 + U_{ref}^2}}$$

Where:

- y_{lab} – molar fraction of the component determined in the laboratory (mol/mol),
- y_{ref} – molar fraction of the reference value of the measured component (mol/mol),
- U_{lab} – laboratory measurement uncertainty (mol/mol),
- U_{ref} – uncertainty of the reference value (mol/mol).

table 14 The Uncertainty for sulphur components

bottle:	reference value			measured value			En
	content	U(xi)		content	U(xi)		
		relative (%)	(mg/m ³)		relative	(mg/m ³)	
DMS	9,26	5,40	0,50	8,99	5,58	0,50	0,38
TBM	9,21	7,49	0,69	9,15	5,57	0,51	0,07
THT	12,34	4,62	0,57	12,80	5,57	0,71	0,50

Conclusion

The validation of the method ISO 19739 for interest compounds was performed according to the performance assessment protocol.

The measurement method is therefore reliable, sensitive and found to be fit-for-purpose.

Annex 1 - Plumbing Diagram

A2.2.5: Validation of the fitness of purpose of the performance assessment protocol developed in A2.1.4 by demonstrating its applicability for total sulphur using GC-SCD

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Introduction

This report describes the performance evaluation of a technique for the measurement of total sulphur using GC-SCD. The following parameters were evaluated: linearity, trueness, repeatability, intermediate precision, limit of detection and selectivity. An uncertainty budget is provided.

Linearity

$$y = 996.68x - 1359.33$$

$$R^2 = 0.88$$

$$y = 1046.41x - 1222.97$$

$$R^2 = 0.98$$

$$y = 1085.52x - 1674.30$$

$$R^2 = 0.91$$

Trueness

Static total sulfur standard (D521792)	10-12-2024	11-12-2024		13-12-2024
Gravimetric standard reference value c_{ref} ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	10.45	10.45	10.45	10.45
Uncertainty of the reference value u_{ref} ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	0.28	0.28	0.28	0.28
Measured value c_m ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	10.43	11.13	11.20	9.64
Uncertainty of measured value u_m ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	0.06	0.05	0.11	0.12
Absolute difference Δ_m ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	0.02	0.68	0.75	0.81
Expanded uncertainty U_Δ ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	0.57	0.57	0.60	0.61
Absolute difference Δ_m (%)	0.18	6.52	7.20	7.73

Where:

$$\Delta_m = |c_m - c_{ref}|$$

And:

$$U_\Delta = 2 \sqrt{u_m^2 + u_{ref}^2}$$

Repeatability

The repeatability of the measurement method was determined using six consecutive measurements of the static check standard D521792. Repeatability was estimated as the relative standard deviation GC-NCD peak area.

Static total sulfur standard (D521792)	10-12-2024	11-12-2024		13-12-2024
Gravimetric standard reference value ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	10.45	10.45	10.45	10.45
RSD (%)	0.87	0.60	1.73	2.29

Within-lab reproducibility (intermediate precision)

Measurements of a static standard were made on 3 separate days. Relative standard deviation of the measured values was used to evaluate the intermediate precision.

Static total sulfur standard (D521792)	10-12-2024	11-12-2024 (average of two)	13-12-2024	RSD (%)
Gravimetric standard reference value c_{ref} ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	10.45	10.45	10.45	-
Uncertainty of the reference value u_{ref} ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	0.28	0.28	0.28	-
Measured value c_m ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	10.43	11.17	9.64	7.33
Uncertainty of measured value u_m ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	0.06	0.12	0.12	-

Limit of detection and quantification

Limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) were evaluated using the signal-to-noise approach, assuming a signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of 3 for LOD and SNR of 10 for LOQ.

$$LOD = \frac{x \times SNR \times N}{S}$$

<i>x</i>	Sample amount fraction $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$	5.27
<i>S</i>	H ₂ S signal height (pA)	403.14
<i>N</i>	noise height (pA)	2.50
	LOD $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$	0.10
	LOQ $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$	0.33

Interferences/selectivity

A sulphur chemiluminescence detector was used which is designed to respond only to sulphur-containing compounds. The separability of different sulphur species using this method was not considered since measurements were of total sulphur.

Uncertainty Budget

The uncertainty budget for this analytical method may be calculated as follows:

$$U = k \sqrt{u_r^2 + u_{day}^2 + \Delta_m^2}$$

Where:

U = the expanded uncertainty of the analytical method;

k = the coverage factor ($k = 2$ for 95% confidence level);

u_r = the relative uncertainty due to measurement repeatability;

u_{day} = the relative uncertainty due to day-to-day variations (within-lab reproducibility); and

Δ_m = the bias of the analytical method.

Repeatability u_r (%)	2.29
Reproducibility u_{day} (%)	7.33
Analytical bias Δ_m (%)	0.81
Expanded uncertainty U (%)	15.44

Summary

Criterion	Target value	Actual value
Working range ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	0.74 - 14.7	3.80 - 16.24
R^2 over working range	>0.99	0.88
LOD ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	≤ 0.22	0.10
LOQ ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	≤ 0.74	0.33
Trueness (%)	≤ 5	7.73
Repeatability (%)	≤ 5	2.29
Intermediate precision (%)	≤ 5	7.33
Expanded uncertainty (%)	≤ 5	15.44